

Can the Decolonization of African Philosophy and Economy be a Reality?

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All forms of colonialism inevitably leave a lasting legacy. The Europeans colonized the African continent, and this social, political, and economic system altered the behaviour of Africans and the African landscape. Academics of various sorts, anthropologists, legal-sociologists, post-colonialists, various educators, are making demands “to do something about” the coloniser society, to penetrate the foreclosed Ness of the theme. Acting regarding the colonial past and present may be defined as rewriting history and committing genocide or denying that there is a colonial past and present, and devaluing knowledge, which is indeed an insult to the casualised cultural ideas and practices. Decolonisation means the end of colonialism. The institutional arrangement of colonialism is known to have had a profound impact on later economic development. Thus, it is an interesting political event to a political economist. This paper looks at how colonialism affected the colonised societies through four imaginations: pre-colonial, colonial encounter, and colonial era. The paper also aims to study the fragmented past, make further invitations to understand the myths offered as well, and demonstrate the fluidity between the past and the present.

Keywords: Decolonisation, colonisation, social and economic organisation, African people

Decolonization is a universal process that engages the colonized and the colonizers in a collective effort towards liberation (Daly, 2016). Unsurprisingly, colonized people undergo decolonisation differently from colonisers do. However, the end goal of these processes is the same. This goal is to cure the mental illness caused by a cultural virus, namely the ideologies of colonisers. Currently, African countries play a dominant role in global economic affairs because they are major producers of raw materials and large consumers of finished goods, as noted by Ocheni and Nwankwo, in 2012. In nations like America and much of Europe, the reasons for destabilization are often readily apparent and frequently attributed to the larger forces at play, which can include the race being blamed, then hapless developing nations, and especially countries from the African region (Khan, 2009). These countries often have a piece of something happening at their end and not generated by the force of the white race (Khan, 2009). African nations face certain conditions unique to them that will need to be addressed through local concoction (Nyoni, 2019).

Definition of Decolonization

Blaser (2013) defines decolonisation as a government system that creates a way to restore the nation to its root government system rather than the one seeded by colonial settlers. Mangcu (2014) presents his interpretation of decolonisation as a nation's pullback from any aggressive and elusive systems that have been imposed by another nation in the search for self-affirmation. According to Wiredu (2004), decolonisation is a process in which the African

people rid themselves of the unwarranted influences of colonialism. However, the fact that the description given to the activity is either not separable from ridding themselves of such influences or works generally, and not in favour of an African point of view. Words like 'decolonisation' have been taken from legitimate writers and used ungracefully as tropes by 'authorities' in some position of power as a way of strengthening colonial social structures, forms of intellectual thought-movement, and places of work (Tuck & Yang, 2012).

Review of Literature

Africanism and Africanization

The policy of Affirmative Action in South Africa pertains to the principle of facilitation of Africanization. The second principle is required to correct the intentional historical imbalances of the past, which developmental imbalances the act of white minority government deliberately built into South African society (Asante, 1980). The Affirmative Action should also include coloureds and Indians, and it should be applied until we achieve a demographically representative balance in the country. Yet Africanization guarantees the development of society. The colonization of African countries has caused economic and political troubles (Asante, 1980).

Colonial capitalism in Africa refers to the penetration of the continent into African societies within the Global capitalist system (Chukwuokolo, 2009). As a result, the phase of colonial capitalism established the view that Africa was only a 'supplier' of raw materials. The economic forces directed agricultural resources towards producing primary products and cash crops, which resulted in widespread hunger and starvation. When it comes to the production of raw materials, there is always a disequilibrium (Farah, Kiamba, & Mazongo, 2011). Decolonization refers to the process of ending colonization, which is aimed at combating imperialism (Green & Bennett, 2018). Colonized nations will liberate and free the caged minds of the colonized, moving that area of emphasis away from Western perspectives as a centre for development.

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Moreover, in the current conversation on decolonization, one witnesses recognition that this African continent, like some of the regional centers, can generate its own epistemology and bursts of development-related accoutrements, and is worthy of equal partnership in the global paradigm generally as well as in the global epistemic community. This was provided in a 2019 publication by Nyoni. It must be reincarnated in Africa's own concrete national knowledge and socio-political and economic systems (Nyoni, 2019). To overcome the negative influences of colonialism that hinder progress, a change in thought is necessary.

The Language of Instruction Challenge

The colonial languages' persistent imposition as the medium of instruction regarding African education is the most obvious debilitating legacy of colonialism in general. In 1976 in South Africa, the brazen venality of the Afrikaner nationalist party government in its attempt to impose Afrikaans on the African majority ruthlessly, it raised the ire and wrath of the African school children in Soweto, who just positively howled out in ear-splitting and strident defiance to the continuing imposition of the "language of the oppressor" on them (Heleta, 2016).

The Current State of the Education System in South Africa

There have been no changes to many aspects of the South African education system. The way the curriculum is structured at schools, the access to quality education, and the way in which many South African schools adhere to a systematic class structure.

In South Africa, children learn in a very colonial space, a characteristic of the education system. Ferris (2017) and as advocated by Dei (2000) the critical evaluation of the colonial liturgies that exist in most schooling and classroom practices (curricula), which affect the creativity and practices of educators, takes place.

Social justice leadership involves moral conversations about the need to negotiate academic success and the need for justice (Lopez 2016). Also, when leaders of educational institutions undertake bold decisions and actions to bring about policies of education (Lopez 2016), so that marginalised children can be better served.

We need university leaders who can create space for reconceptualising and rethinking, and understand that there cannot be one notion of social justice. Through the introduction of a new epistemology and ontology, the necessity of disrupting a Eurocentric consciousness through decolonising education and the concepts of meritocracy that exist in education and society needs to be done, which has privileged some.

Alternative ways of knowing must be appreciated, understood, and practised in moving the South African education system forward. The experts and practitioners must join hands in putting theory into practice to achieve it. The education system still struggles with the colonial legacy in the situation of the changes in the global climate and social contexts. The educational structure of South Africa has not changed in many ways.

The educational system in South Africa still feels the impact of colonization due to the centralizing and systemic influences that perpetuate the class structure in South Africa and access to quality education (Lopez & Rugano 2018). Social justice leadership includes strategies for leading that challenge university leaders to

appreciate the many possibilities for diversifying leaders, challenging the dominant discourse and knowledge that prevails (Heleta, 2016).

Decolonisation and the Face of South African Schools

The system of education introduced by colonialism tends to uproot students from all that they originally are and reform them into a kind of foreign being (Wa Thiong'o, 1998). A successful individual acquires the habits of the coloniser at the expense of the original nation (Alexander & Bloch, 2004).

These dimensions play an important role in the education field, which has a serious impact on the minds of the students. This could be why Omodan and Dube (2020) suggested decolonizing the minds at the universities. It is pertinent to note at this stage that there are subjects that hardly get learnt in South African languages, but only in two imported languages, which are English and Afrikaans. At first glance, South African students feel that these two languages are more valuable than their indigenous African Languages. In the same country, the educational system appears to function at least two levels; there is a general level/public one, and there is, at the same time, a specific level/private one (Uleanya, Rugbeer, & Olaniran, 2019). "South Africa has not completely divorced itself from its colonial status and is still in full recuperation from the colonial plague, which all assumed to be development" (Mohoto, 2015).

The Possibilities of Indigenous Languages as Methods of Instruction

It is believed that even our South African languages are not as impoverished as most people think them to be. Some people believe that outside anthropologists and linguists worked to exclude literacy practices and traditions of the people who speak a Bantu language. This is to create a deliberate misunderstanding that Africans cannot develop an education that produces a written account of their ways of knowing and major activities (Raum, 1993). Indeed, this is a deliberate act of colonialism to undermine and erase African contributions (Rwantabagu, 2011). Tisani (2004) and LeGrange (2016) see some happenings in Africa's academic institutions and argue that there is another error that Westerners come to Africa and study all other things except Africanness and Afrocentricity.

Language gives people a voice. It is a sign of society and has a history with the people who speak it (Blaser, 2013). Education is basically the foundation that is going to make the people and their traditions (Lockett, 2016). If a person learns another tradition's language and culture without learning their own seriously, they get disconnected from their identity.

A nation that is embarrassed to learn and teach in its own language is unfree. Consequently, the South African state and linguists have a heavy load to carry to do something about it. Parents send children to private schools with high expectations that they will be special victims. And so, it seems. The current schooling situation of private school learners results in reproducing the existing colonial system that privileges English and Afrikaans at the expense of African languages (Hurst, 2016).

Theoretical Framework

The 1980s saw Asante's Afrocentric philosophy become the foundation of this study. According to Asante (1980), knowledge is leaving the African world to be generated in the African world, not

just in African lands but also in the Diaspora. The theory highlights the need to obliterate the ideas of colonialism and Eurocentric thinking, which are enmeshed in economic theory. The Afrocentric philosophy of Asante is one of the important aspects of the theoretical framework of this paper. Through the concept of the Yoruba philosophy, he emphasises many of the research objectives of decolonising economic experiences in the African political economy. The theories are related to professional learning communities and the effective processes that are required in academic life.

Social Realism Theory

Quinn (2012) and Vorster and Quinn (2015) argue that the decolonisation of education can only happen through relevant pedagogy and the curriculum, which will reflect the reality of the learner's own environment and contexts. Margaret Archer's (1995) work, situated in the social realist tradition, gives rise to an important insight into the ontology of academic learning activities. Critical realism assures us that epistemology cannot be the same as ontology. Academics play a role in developing a deeper understanding of decolonisation of education in multilayered contexts. Critical realism relies on individual lived experiences to construct insights about reality and analyse structural and mechanism aspects, which can be described as real contexts (Asante, 1980).

The colonial structures and nature of education at South African universities have brought about the need for realities in higher education. These realities have been seen differently in the contexts of the various stakeholders (Maldonado-Torres, 2011; Luckett, 2016). Therefore, teaching and delivery practices of the academic staff need to be totally restructured and repositioned for decolonised education.

Professional groups help these scholars understand what they need to teach. They also help them learn how to teach these things. Moreover, the methodology and content to which they are exposed are relevant to South African contexts. According to Vorster and Quinn (2017), if institutional cultures and practices are to become decolonised, there is an urgent need to geostrategise academic staff for productivity; this must be the priority. Employment in South African universities rapidly turns into a question of what this implies.

More productive and effective academics will teach, in an assessment, either by placing or integrating their students to observe their needs, testing learning. Educational transformations have been informed by social realism as a contextualisation of real dynamics. Grasping the arguments, it is the arguments of Margaret Archer (1995) that academics will approach the educational experiences. Social realism is related to a social interaction situated in any individual with a socio-cultural variable whose dynamism would be reflected in the contexts of higher education.

Students' learning can be translated to respond to the need to have realities in learning structures and contents that may respectively suit local contexts and, at some stage, mean competition with their contemporaries in academic life (Le Grange, 2016; Luckett, 2016). Learning communities make it possible for academic growth to become effective and realistic, to the extent that participants acquire some knowledge as to how things ought to be, are deliberated and erected, as well as inhibiting contextual limitations which may serve as detrimental means of having the transformation take place.

The educational institutions' inclusion of social realism in

professional learning communities for academic staff development is based on Archer's (1995) view of learning communities in universities. Also, mouting interdependency, intercreativity of people, culture, and structures, where the interrelationship causes intertwining with one another.

South African universities have been influenced by long-standing core structures that have deeply penetrated their academic structures (Le Grange, 2016). Learning communities can therefore be effective means to recreate or ensure academic activities or endeavours, to ensure realism in social contexts of education in South Africa.

Social Transformation Theory

According to this theory, changes in the university setting either happen in a blended way or through a domain of being that is interconnected with societal demand (Fomunyam, 2015). To transform a reality, Fomunyam (2015) developed four main anchors that are indeed interrelated and interdependent. These are resistance to change, advocacy of change, alternative vision, and nation-building. Those who bring change will always guarantee and create evidence for the need for change in the present structure or context.

According to Fomunyam (2015), Vorster and Quinn (2017), the academic factor is the reason for their maximally noticed, who are finding decolonization for South African universities. According to these minds, the education should throw away the content, methodology, and educational structure of the apartheid legacy. Educational structure was so diverse during the apartheid era; hence, one feels the urgent need for a certain transformation that will reflect real Africanism. Racial diversity present in the cultural structures must be resolved within their field of the poorer states represented in others by such effects on the economic and political influence of some nations (Ruming, 2014).

Method

This involved undertaking a qualitative case study on a country or region of Africa to explore the historical, cultural, and economic bases for the development of economic narratives. By following this method, one can see the situations of the region and how the colonisation history has left a mark on their economic thinking.

Decolonising Economic Narratives

Decolonization is the process of ending colonialism. Decolonization means freeing the minds of the colonized that are caged by the removal of the Western view as a central locus for the development of knowledge. The aim of deconstructionist decolonialisation discourse, then, is to allow for acknowledgment of Africa as an equal global partner and a regional centre of epistemology generation, along with all its development complexities (Nyoni, 2019). In short, Africa should reclaim its own indigenous know-how and its social, political, and economic systems (Nyoni, 2019). Decolonisation refers to dismantling the social systems set up by colonial powers to exploit and dominate individuals. It is not enough to just have independence because decolonization requires a change in thinking. We must get rid of the harmful colonial way of thinking, which has held us back.

Fanon (2008) said that "the black-and-white confrontation" has created "an immense psycho-existential complex". Fanon (2008) in his *Black Skin, White Masks*, aimed to free the black man of the stock of complexes created by the colonial milieu (Fanon, 2008). Fanon (2008) thus emphasized the need for black persons to deal

with the consequences of colonialism. Whether or not true African education will be preserved will be determined by collective action through decolonization that acts to protect cultural values, identities, and curricula (Nyoni, 2019).

For the Western-initiated educational curricula to be devoid of their toxic and Western-inspired nuances and story lines, African voices must be allowed to correct them. As a result, the creation of knowledge is crucial for the development of the Third World. To achieve peaceful coexistence and economic standing, knowledge creation will not only be beneficial but also essential.

Recommendations

We must decolonise the learning system so that people are not underestimating the level of the learning system, but it is meant for ensuring the quality education is kept at the level which is intended in the African context. So, the first thing that must be done is confronting the issue of decolonisation, and for this purpose, the government must be people-centred, the kind of government that, for example, is willing and ready to enact pro-poor legislation.

Fanon explains that colonialism and imperialism harm blacks and their society. Thus, it is essential to get rid of it entirely (Fanon, 2008). It's also necessary that greater emphasis is placed on encouraging the self-reliant and indigenous solutions. There is also the need for the indigenous people to use their own knowledge, languages, and cultures that generate vernacular cultures, as that will then become the basis of an African-centred political economy (Heleta, 2016; Nyoni, 2019).

Strengthening Relationship with Community: Bridging the education institution and community gap. Build an involvement of the community in the design of the curriculum so that what is needed by the community and the values of the community can fit in. The educational process is the setting that transmits culture. Thus, the educational process can transform the health crisis paradigms in society. As a result, the need to reform the educational curriculum all over the sub-Saharan African countries is significant to put in place a real mental and intellectual self-government.

Furthermore, another impetus is being given where participants are encouraged to understand global issues in a national and cultural context in which they exist, as their interest in understanding global issues from varied cultural perspectives. Bringing about a balanced understanding of worldwide happenings, but which at the same time perpetuates and celebrates the diversity of the cultures of that country (Nyoni, 2019).

The government has the strength of political will, economic power, and control of the "means of production". All these are necessary for the government to bring about decolonisation. It should be a matter of concern for academia to work in tandem and share each other's experiences, knowledge, and strive towards ways of improvement and development of teaching pedagogy, as well as how students can be involved in the same. This will then mean revising the course, specifically, to upgrade teachers in this sense. Here, there will be the opportunity for teachers to meet and get in touch with each other in their work of sharing and improvement.

Conclusion

An explanation of decolonisation meaning has been provided in the article. That is, decolonisation refers to the removal of imperialist conceptions from society. Therefore, it is a movement for the

upholding of social justice, and the article has made clear the necessity of decolonisation. The article has once more shown that the decolonisation of teaching methods, although not an easy fix, is achievable in the higher education institutions of the Republic of South Africa, as they avail themselves of avenues which are not just symbolic, but which have worth in the enlarging of the knowledge of the lecturers and the learners. No decolonisation of teaching can ever be said to be complete unless the knowledge, skills, and ideas are thoroughly disseminated. It is unfair to create a poor condition of affairs within the courts, which will herald a move for the progress of all kinds of skill, into which may enter the legal work in institutional and emotional fields.

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